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RISK FOR VIOLENCE SCREENING IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Healthcare workers experience high rates of workplace violence by patients. The highest risk of violence is seen in EDs, where patients first arrive to seek medical care. Because the ED is considered a high risk-for-violence setting, ED nurses are more likely to face violence than nurses working in other units. **Aim:** The aim of this quality improvement project was to revise the current workplace violence prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool and evaluate its efficacy. **Method:** Using the plan-do-study-act framework, a validated risk-for-violence screening tool with a scoring system and assault prevention strategies were used and evaluated. Steps to implementing the project included the following: (1) adult and pediatric patients screened at the walk-in Triage for risk criteria for violence, (2) a scoring system based on low, moderate, and high risk for violence, (3) medical record tracking system flagged with a golden hand symbol to alert staff to moderate to high risk for violence, and (4) implementation of assault prevention strategies. **Results:** There was a total of 3857 screening tools completed using the QOVPRAO with 97% (n= 3759) of patients scoring at a low, 1% (n=65) moderate, and <1% (n=33) at high risk for violence. Fifty-nine percent of Triage nurses reported that the QOVPRAO adequately identified patients at risk for violence, 43% reported that the tool was easy to complete and quickly assessed risk, and 54% preferred to have the QOVPRAO tool replace the previous tool. Physical assaults on staff were recorded and tracked for a period of six weeks from the end of December 2023 to early February 2024, through a retrospective review of the hospital's online incident report system. Patient-to-staff physical assaults during the project were zero. **Conclusion:** Screening for the risk of violence upon arrival and implementing strategies to prevent assaults present an opportunity to ensure and improve the safety of ED nurses. By implementing such preventive measures and providing support for staff, hospitals can create a safer working environment for ED nurses and improve overall patient care.

Keywords: workplace violence, emergency department, emergency nurses, workplace aggression, violence prevention, risk for violence screening tools

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vi
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	3
Purpose Statement.....	4
Framework for Violence Screening in the Emergency Department.....	4
The Plan Do Study Act Cycle.....	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Overview of Workplace Violence	9
COVID-19 and WPV	11
Risk Factors/Predictors of WPV.....	12
Nurse-Related Factors.....	12
Environmental Factors.....	13
Individual Patient Risk Factors.....	14
WPV Prevention and Interventions	15
WPV De-escalation Techniques	16
WPV Deflection Techniques	17
Risk for Violence Assessment Tools	17
Restrictive Interventions	19
Additional WPV Prevention Interventions	20
Summary and Evidence Limitations.....	21
METHODS	23
Design	23
Setting	23
Usual Triage Process	24
Participants.....	25
Ethical Considerations	25
Procedure Using PDSA Framework	25
Plan	26
Do.....	27
Pre-Implementation Survey	27

Post-Implementation Survey.....	29
The QOVPROA Risk Assessment Tool With Safety Interventions.....	30
Interventions Based on Risk Level	30
Golden Hand Visual Alert for Violence Risk	32
Study	33
Act.....	33
RESULTS	34
DISCUSSION	36
Limitations	38
Implications for Practice.....	38
Conclusion	39
REFERENCES	40
APPENDIX A: Figure 1: PDSA Cycle.....	51
APPENDIX B: Figure 2: Integration of the PDSA Cycle:.....	52
APPENDIX C: Permission to use the QOVPROA	53
APPENDIX D: Pre-Implementation Survey	54
APPENDIX E: Permission to Use CCPAI Tool.....	55
APPENDIX F: Post-Implementation Survey.....	56
APPENDIX G: QOVPROA Violence Risk Assessment Tool	57
APPENDIX H: Propensity for Violent Behavior Care Management Protocol	58
APPENDIX I: Symbol of Golden Hand.....	62
APPENDIX J: Table 1: Participant Demographics	63
APPENDIX K: Results of QOVPROA Scores.....	64
APPENDIX L: Table 2: CCPAI Survey Results:.....	65
APPENDIX M: Figure 3: Mean Scores for CCPAI.....	66
APPENDIX N: Figure 4: Mean Gender Scores for Handling Physical Aggression	67

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Background

Violence in the healthcare setting is a growing concern (Kafle et al., 2022). According to data from the United States (U.S.) Bureau of Labor Statistics (2022), healthcare worker injuries caused by violence have steadily increased over the last decade. Incidence data revealed that in 2020, healthcare practitioners sustained 23% of 37,060 nonfatal injuries in the workplace (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). A Press Ganey (2022) survey estimated that an average of two nurses are physically assaulted every hour in the U.S. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2023), between 8% and 38% of nurses have been victims of healthcare violence during the course of their profession.

Occupational violence is defined as the “act or threat of violence, ranging from verbal abuse to physical assaults directed toward persons at work or on duty” (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health [NIOSH], 2022, p. 1). While the numbers reported above are alarming, NIOSH (2022) acknowledges that the numbers may be underestimated due to the healthcare workers’ perception that being verbally assaulted may be seen as a normal part of the work environment. Ashton et al. (2018) assert that underreporting may be due to institutions lacking policies and procedures or reporting systems. In addition, management may discourage healthcare workers from reporting, and staff who report may fear judgment (Ashton et al., 2018).

Workplace violence (WPV) has a wide range of negative effects on healthcare workers, ranging from psychological trauma to physical injury, or can even result in death. The effects of WPV on healthcare workers can impair patient care and result in job dissatisfaction and high turnover (Ferri et al., 2020). Frequent WPV exposure may also decrease health-related quality of life, lead to absence from work, cause low morale, and decrease employee productivity (Copeland & Henry, 2017; Kafle et al., 2022). Healthcare workers are at greater risk of requiring

time off from work due to emotional effects and physical injuries from WPV (NIOSH, 2022).

The consequences of WPV on healthcare workers are troubling and additional measures must be taken to address the issue.

The highest risk of violence in the acute care setting is in Emergency Departments (EDs), where patients first arrive to seek medical care (Ferri et al., 2020). An estimated 529,000 nonfatal injuries from WPV were seen in hospital Eds between 2015–2019 (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2019). In general, nurses are one of the professional healthcare workers most exposed to WPV because they spend most of their time providing direct care to patients who may be physically or mentally ill (Ramacciati et al., 2019). Because the ED is considered a high-risk for violence setting, ED nurses are four times more likely to face violence than nurses in other units (Sharifi et al., 2020).

Violence in the ED may be in the form of verbal abuse or physical violence (Sharifi et al., 2020). The ED environment is often unpredictable, chaotic, and overcrowded. ED nurses encounter patients with a high propensity for violence due to drug use, intoxication, acute psychiatric disorders, cognitive impairments, disease progression, and severe pain. Prolonged waiting times in the ED add to patients' and their relatives' high anxiety or stress levels, leading to an increased risk for violence (d'Ettoire et al., 2018). Ferri et al. (2020) reported that 96% of triage nurses in the ED experienced at least one episode of violence from patients or visitors in the previous year, concluding that high stress and anxiety levels in the ED may lead to WPV. Furthermore, Tiesman et al. (2023) found that the stress and uncertainty of the coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19) pandemic had further increased WPV. During the COVID-19 pandemic, international studies discovered a high prevalence of violence among healthcare workers, significantly impacting their mental health (Tiesman et al., 2023).

National agencies proposed recommendations and strategies to mitigate WPV (Emergency Nurses Association [ENA], 2022). The Joint Commission's (TJC) Environment of Care (EC) standards require healthcare facilities to have a written plan describing how they ensure the safety of their patients, staff, and visitors. Institutions must conduct risk assessments to determine the risk of WPV and develop strategies and a response plan to be enacted when a violent act occurs (TJC, 2018). In 2019, the ENA endorsed an initiative called "*No Silence on ED Violence*" (ENA, 2019). Part of this project includes a WPV prevention toolkit to guide ED settings in preventing WPV. The ENA (2022) toolkit recommends that Eds use a risk assessment tool to assess and mitigate patient risk factors. Various violence assessment screening tools have been developed to decrease violence in healthcare; however, there are few validated tools for specific use in the ED (Ghosh et al., 2019). Violence risk assessment is essential for reducing ED nurses' exposure to violence.

Problem Statement

WPV incidences in the ED commonly occur and continue to increase (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2019). In the past two years, from 2021 to 2023, there was an increase in the incidence of WPV in the ED of a 453-bed metropolitan public teaching hospital where this QI project took place. The hospital serves an average of 90,000 patients annually. The patient population includes people experiencing homelessness, victims of gang violence, and patients with mental health and substance use disorders. In 2020, in view of growing concern about WPV, a violence screening tool called the Historical Clinical Risk Management 20, Version 3 (HCR-20-3) was piloted in the ED where this QI project occurred (Douglas et al., 2014). This tool was originally used at a partner hospital and was later adopted by this hospital. However, the tool was not validated in the ED setting and did not provide risk stratification. In addition, assessment

completion of the HCR-20-3 was low at 63%. Subsequently, from 2021 to 2022, the number of physical assaults on ED nurses increased by approximately 25%. Due to the increased staff assaults, the plan was to revise the Risk for Violence protocol and use a new validated screening tool that included assault prevention strategies based on the hospital's violence prevention protocol. The QI project outcome was to evaluate if these measures would reduce the incidence of physical assaults in the ED. Nurses' self-confidence in managing patient aggression was evaluated using these evidence-based measures.

Purpose Statement

The aim of this QI project was to revise the current WPV prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool and evaluate its efficacy in identifying potentially violent patients in the ED of a large metropolitan teaching hospital. Short-term outcome measures included triage nurse completion rates of the tool with the goal of at least 80%. Additionally, the initiation of assault prevention strategies on at-risk for violence patients was evaluated. The project's long-term goal was to reduce WPV episodes after implementing the revised protocol.

Framework for Violence Screening Assessment in the Emergency Department

Applying a suitable framework to a QI project can provide structure and organization for the project manager (Reynolds & Granger, 2023). QI models provide a systematic, formal framework for implementing QI processes in clinical practice (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2020). Various QI models exist to help implement change, collect and analyze data, and ensure the change has the intended impact. Langley et al. (2009) suggest using the Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) cycle as an effective trial-and-learning methodology. This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project used the Model for Improvement PDSA cycle to

implement and evaluate a new violence risk assessment tool and include it as part of the protocol in the ED.

The Plan Do Study Act Cycle

The Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) (2023) uses the Model for Improvement framework to guide improvement projects. This model was initially developed in 1996 by the Association for Process Improvement (API), a partner organization of the IHI (IHI, 2023). The Model for Improvement is divided into two phases. The first phase asks three questions: 1) “What are we trying to accomplish?”, 2) How will we know that a change is an improvement?, and 3) What change can we make that will result in improvement?” The second phase of the Model for Improvement involves testing the intervention and is called the Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) cycle.

The PDSA cycle was developed in the 1920s by Walter Shewhart and was later revised to an abbreviated version in 1993 by Dr. William Edwards Deming (The W. Edwards Deming Institute, 2023a). The PDSA cycle is a four-step process improvement model (IHI, 2023b). The cycle begins with a plan and ends with an action (Provost & Murray, 2022). The first step is to develop the plan in which the project’s “who,” “what,” “when,” and “where” tasks are assigned (IHI, 2023). Details of the project are outlined in this phase. In the Do Phase, the plan is implemented, and the practice change is pilot-tested. Data and results obtained are then analyzed in the Study Phase. In the last phase of the Act, a decision is made to adopt, adapt, or abandon the practice change based on the evaluation included in the prior step. In Adoption, the change would be accepted and integrated into the project. If the intervention needs to be adapted, changes are made before starting another cycle. By abandoning, no improvement would be

made, and the intervention would be eliminated (IHI, 2023). The PSDA Model for Improvement is shown in Appendix A.

The PSDA model is an improvement framework used in violence risk assessment interventions. In a study by Larson et al. (2019), PSDA cycles improved communication between ED and inpatient nurses regarding violent patients admitted to the ward. Similarly, Okundolor et al. (2021) used the PSDA model to decrease staff assaults in a psychiatric ED. Six PSDA cycles tested the use of a visual sign outside a violent patient's room to increase communication among team members. The survey respondents believed that the signage helped communicate a patient's potential for violence (Okundolor et al., 2021).

Applying the PSDA Model for Improvement to the present project began by answering the three questions. The first question was, "What are we trying to accomplish?" The project included assessing a patient's risk for violence using a risk-for-violence screening tool. After the assessment, violence prevention interventions were to be implemented. The second question, "How will we know that a change is an improvement?" was determined by an increase in the number of patients flagged as high risk for violence over six weeks. Over a longer evaluation period, there would be a decrease in the number of physical assaults by patients. The third question asked was, "What change can we make that will result in improvement?" This was answered by evaluating that ED nurses were assessing all patients who presented to the ED for risk of violence using the tool and then carrying out the violence prevention protocol. By ensuring the completion of the assessment tool by at least 80%, and evaluating if the protocol was initiated, it was possible to evaluate if any improvement was accomplished.

In accordance with the first stage of the PSDA cycle, a QI team was formed. This QI team was comprised of data extractors for the ED, and the project lead (PL). Baseline data was

collected and reviewed on the number of physical assaults in the ED by patients toward staff using the hospital's safety intelligence (SI) incident reporting system. After reviewing the literature, a validated violence screening tool was selected to use in triage. The Do Stage involved training the nurses at Triage on the risk assessment tool. Nurses completed the risk-for-violence screening tool for all patients presenting to the Triage Unit of the ED. Nurses then initiated the violence prevention protocol for all patients who were identified as at risk of violence. The Study Stage for this project involved reviewing the data and analyzing the QI project results. Completion rates of the tool and initiation of the violence prevention protocol were evaluated. The results of the data were shared with the QI team. Based on the data results and nurse feedback, the Act stage involved an overall evaluation of the practice change to determine the next steps. At this stage, it was decided to adopt the change. Figure 2 in Appendix B contains a detailed diagram of the integration of the PDSA model.

Review of the Literature

A literature review was conducted to investigate the research on WPV in the healthcare setting (Grove & Gray, 2019). The electronic databases Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MEDLINE), Public/Publisher Medline (PubMed), and Google Scholar were searched. MeSH and keywords included “workplace violence,” “emergency department,” “emergency nurses,” “workplace aggression,” “violence prevention,” and “risk for violence screening tools.” These keyword searches yielded 292 articles. The search was then filtered to limit the articles to full text, peer-reviewed, and those published within the last five years, yielding 82 results. Studies were excluded if they were not written in English or included intimate partner violence, interpersonal violence, or domestic violence. Each abstract and full text was reviewed for alignment with the topic of WPV and resulted in 26 articles used for this literature review.

The 26 study designs included randomized controlled trials, quasi-experimental studies, observational studies, and qualitative studies. Some of the studies used mixed methods. Many of the studies were international, reflecting the fact that WPV is a problem experienced worldwide. The level of evidence ranged from level II to VI (Grove & Gray, 2019). The articles were organized into the following categories, which were used as the topics addressed in this literature review: 1) WPV overview, 2) risk factors or predictors of WPV, and 3) WPV prevention and interventions.

The purpose of this DNP project was to revise the current workplace violence prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool and evaluate its efficacy in identifying potentially violent patients in the ED. The over-arching goal was to reduce patient-to-staff assaults. The prevalence and precipitants of WPV in healthcare

were discussed, as well as strategies to mitigate it. The literature review concluded with a summary of the findings.

Overview of Workplace Violence in the Healthcare Setting

In the U.S., acts of violence and other injuries are the third leading cause of fatal occupational injuries (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2022), 761 of the 5,333 fatal workplace injuries in the U.S. in 2019 were cases of intentional injury by another person. Healthcare workers were at an elevated risk of encountering WPV due to their direct interaction with high-risk for violence patients (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2020; Occupational Safety and Health Administration [OSHA], 2016; WHO, 2002). The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2022) reported that of the 20,050 workers who experienced WPV trauma, 76% were healthcare workers. Similarly, according to the WHO (2023), nearly a quarter of workplace violence occurred in healthcare institutions worldwide, and healthcare professionals were 16 times more likely to be attacked than employees in other professions. Nurses had frequently been the targets of WPV and in 2020, the CDC reported that physical assaults occurred at a rate of 13.2, while non-physical violent events occurred at 38.8 per 100 nurses yearly. Emergency room nurses had the highest rate of WPV episodes among nursing staff, with more than 70% experiencing some form of WPV (Al-Maskari et al., 2020; Alsharari et al., 2022).

The OSHA (2016) described WPV as any act or threat of physical violence, intimidation, or other threatening disruptive workplace behavior, ranging from verbal to physical assaults. Similarly, the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) defined WPV as “violent acts, either physical or verbal assaults, directed towards other people at work or on duty” (NIOSH, 2020, p. 1). Some studies that attempt to quantify the types and number of WPV

episodes emphasized the urgency of reporting all assaults and not just reporting assaults due to physical injury (Copeland & Henry, 2017; Kafle et al., 2022). While it is true that physical injury is easy to recognize, the effect of verbal and psychological abuse must also be recognized and reported (McGuire et al., 2023). Boles et al. (2023) acknowledged that non-physical abuse can harm psychological well-being and escalate to physical violence. It is, therefore, important to convey the need for nurses to manage and report all forms of WPV, regardless of physical injury. One of the difficulties in estimating the scope of WPV is that incidences are not always reported. Approximately 52.4% of the nurses in a study by Alsharari et al. (2022) failed to report that they had been a victim of WPV. The most common reason cited was that the assault would not be taken seriously. Other studies also attempted to identify why nursing staff does not report WPV (Arnetz et al., 2017; Dafny & Beccaria, 2020; Copeland & Henry, 2017). Arnetz et al. (2017) surveyed 269 nurses employed in hospitals with an electronic reporting system. Employees were more likely to report if there was a physical injury; however, the rate of reporting was extremely low at 40%. Copeland and Henry (2017) found that more than half of their study's 57 ED staff members did not report incidents because they felt that it was not necessary since no injuries took place. Dafny and Beccaria (2020) conducted focus group interviews and found similar barriers to reporting. Overall, the common explanation in these studies was nurses' overwhelming attitude that violence is expected in the acute healthcare setting (Copeland & Henry, 2017; Dafny & Beccaria, 2020).

Numerous studies supported that experiencing a violent incident had a serious impact on nurses' mental health. Boles et al. (2023) found that nurses who suffered a physical attack reported feeling anger, shock, and betrayal after each incident. Copeland and Henry (2017) asserted that repeated exposure to violence results in burnout, traumatic stress, and a decrease in

the quality of care for patients. A qualitative study by Gillespie and Berry (2023) described nurses as feeling fearful, anxious, and helpless after experiencing an attack, with 3.6% having thoughts of retaliating against the aggressor immediately after the attack. Providing emotional support enhanced resilience for individuals who experienced WPV. However, according to Gillespie & Berry (2023), only 1% of the 167 nurses who reported violence received such support after the incident.

The consequences of WPV extended to patients and the organization (Powell et al., 2023; Gillespie & Berry, 2023). When aggression occurred, all available staff on the unit converged, leaving other patients who needed care (Gillespie & Berry, 2023). This action resulted in delayed care and triggered other emergencies in the ED. According to OSHA (2016), organizations were negatively impacted by WPV in the following ways: 1) reduced productivity, 2) absenteeism, and 3) direct medical expenses due to employee injuries. In addition, employee injuries led to workers' compensation losses of thousands of dollars, along with additional costs for overtime or temporary staffing (OSHA, 2016). Preventing WPV was not only essential for the safety and well-being of nurses and patients but also to avoid the expensive consequences that organizations faced due to WPV.

COVID-19 and WPV

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic increased the incidence of WPV (Brigo et al., 2022; McGuire et al., 2023). According to Byon et al. (2021), during the COVID-19 pandemic, nurses experienced more physical and verbal abuse from their patients, visitors, and/or family members. In addition, nurses caring for patients with COVID-19 experienced more WPV than nurses who cared for other patients (Byon et al., 2021). Brigo et al. (2022) reported

that monthly assaults against healthcare personnel increased from 13.5 per month pre-COVID-19 to 27.2 per month during the pandemic.

Nurses worked under stressful conditions during the pandemic. In studies by Byon et al. (2021) and Liu et al. (2021), nurses reported a general increase in anxiety, staff shortages, and more physical abuse from patients. Byon et al. (2021) reported that nurses who cared for COVID-19 patients experienced 73% more verbal abuse from patients, families, or visitors than those who did not. Brigo et al. (2022) acknowledged that the increased workload and exhaustion contributed to increased aggression because overwhelmed nurses are hindered in their ability to manage violent situations. Studies revealed that lacking organizational resources, such as personal protective equipment, increased staff stress levels during this time (Byon et al, 2021; Tiesman et al., 2023). Throughout this and future healthcare crises, organizations needed to be proactive in prioritizing nurses' well-being and safety.

Risk Factors and Predictors of Workplace Violence

To ensure the safety of healthcare personnel and improve patient care, it was essential to identify risk factors and the nature of violence. This enabled effective planning and interventions to address the issue. Factors contributing to WPV identified in the literature included nurse-related, environmental, and individual patient factors (Al-Maskari et al., 2020; d'Ettoire et al, 2018; Ferri et al., 2020). Recognizing these factors was a way of foreseeing and implementing strategies to provide a safer workplace.

Nurse-Related Risk Factors

Nurse-related risk factors of WPV included poor communication skills, age, and years of experience (Berlanda et al., 2019; Copeland & Henry, 2017; Pich et al., 2017). More experienced ED nurses and nurses over 40 had a decreased risk for violence in an Italian study by Berlanda et

al. (2019). These researchers concluded that nurses with more experience in the profession were more effective at managing patients' violent episodes (Berlanda et al., 2019). Poor nurse communication skills also placed nurses at greater risk for WPV (Copeland & Henry, 2017). Additional nurse-related risk factors included the inability to effectively communicate with or de-escalate agitated patients (Chang et al., 2022; Lamont & Brunero, 2018). Considering these findings, WPV prevention training programs were geared at improving the communication and technical skills of nurses to promote a culture of safety in the healthcare environment (Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Sharifi et al., 2020). In addition to providing training, annual competencies included a refresher skill review to ensure nurses were able to recognize and diffuse violent encounters (Kynoch et al., 2024).

Environmental Risk Factors

The ED is the first point of contact for patients seeking emergency medical attention, which can make ED nurses more vulnerable to verbal or physical threats than other healthcare professionals (McGuire et al., 2023). Prolonged waiting times, in combination with overcrowding, public access to EDs, and high-stress conditions, predisposed nurses in the ED to experience more violent encounters (d'Ettorre et al., 2018; Pich et al, 2017). Additionally, environmental noise and excessive activity were triggers of behavioral health crises (Winokur et al., 2018).

According to a study by Ramacciati et al. (2019), the most common places where violence occurred were Triage (85.9%), the waiting room (41.2%), and the reception area (37.3%). The Triage Unit was a particularly high-risk area in the ED. Structurally, Triage was located next to the waiting room, where patients first checked in when they arrived at the ED. Patients with acute medical and/or behavioral health crises were generally first seen in Triage

and were in close proximity to healthcare providers. According to Oztas et al. (2023), patients became violent when expectations were unrealistic or patient requests for intervention were not medically appropriate. Ferri et al. (2020) reported that 63% of violence incidents occurred in the waiting room, linking WPV to patient anxiety caused partly by prolonged wait times. Patterns of violence were also examined in a study of peak ED time which showed violent episodes most often occur on weekends (Al-Maskari et al., 2020). In a study of four acute care settings in Oman, Al-Maskari et al. (2020) found that 68.4% of physical violence and 82.8% of verbal assaults occurred on Saturday and Sunday. Moreover, 78.9% of assaults occurred in the evening shift compared to 93.1% on the night shift (Al-Maskari et al., 2020). Increases in aggression by patients during these times were explained by low staffing and busy ED times (Copeland & Henry, 2017). It was important to recognize that environmental factors played a role in increasing the risk of violence. If feasible, measures should be taken to modify the work setting and promote a safe working environment.

Individual Patient Risk Factors

Individual patient risk factors were the most common precursors to violence. Patient risk factors were stratified into clinical and non-clinical categories (Cabilan & Johnston, 2021; d’Ettorre et al., 2018). Dementia, schizophrenia, acute stress episodes, suicidal ideation, alcohol and drug intoxication, pain, and a history of violence were found to be clinical patient risk factors for physical violence in patients (Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Pich et al., 2017). The best predictor of violence was a previous history of violence. An approach to preventing and managing violent episodes was a risk assessment, followed by flagging the chart with a high risk for violence alert in the EMR (Mallet-Smith et al., 2023). This system helped communicate safety-related concerns, such as a patient’s history of violent behavior, to staff who may

encounter the patient (Ferron et al., 2022). Non-clinical patient risk factors contributing to violence included a lack of trust in doctors, unmet needs, and discontent with the course of therapy (Berlanda et al., 2019). While many of the patient risk factors could be resolved, a risk assessment was deemed to be essential and guided appropriate precautions to minimize the risk of violence (Cabilan & Johnston, 2021; Kim et al., 2022).

Workplace Violence Prevention and Interventions

In 2017, California Senate Bill 3342 (SB 3342), Violence Prevention in Healthcare, was passed and required all hospitals to have written WPV prevention plans that safeguard their employees (California Department of Industrial Relations, 2023). In 2022, the Joint Commission introduced new accreditation standards related to WPV (TJC, 2021). The standards mandated that each healthcare facility set up a system to monitor, report, and train staff to curtail increasing WPV. To accomplish the goal of a system-based WPV prevention protocol, nursing staff must be trained to screen and take precautions when patients are assessed as being at high risk for violence. Research had demonstrated that WPV training programs improved the knowledge, skills, and confidence of nurses who experienced WPV in the healthcare environment (Arnetz et al., 2017; Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Sharifi et al., 2020). WPV training programs involved a set of learning activities geared towards educating nurses on applying strategies to prevent and manage violence in the workplace. Training programs included preventative protocols with de-escalation techniques, deflection techniques, and risk assessment checklists (Chang et al., 2022; Kumari et al., 2022). These violence prevention strategies were noted to positively affect nurses' ability to manage violent situations and will be discussed in the next section (Chang et al., 2022; Gaynes et al., 2017; Lamont & Brunero, 2018).

Workplace Violence De-escalation Techniques

The risk of assault could be prevented or minimized if employers took appropriate precautions using de-escalation techniques. De-escalation techniques were designed to prevent violent episodes from escalating to physical aggression (Gaynes et al., 2017). De-escalation training prepared nurses for WPV prevention through situational awareness, leading to early recognition, and prompt intervention to manage behavior prior to the patient becoming physically aggressive (Casey et al., 2019; Chang et al, 2022). According to Timmins et al. (2023), de-escalation training was a best-practice approach in mitigating WPV, as it positively affected the safety of healthcare workers. Examples of de-escalation techniques included having the staff show empathy and use a non-judgmental approach, respecting the patient's individual space, keeping the tone of voice and body language neutral, and using a team approach (Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Sharifi et al., 2020). A team approach was limited to two staff members working together to de-escalate a potentially aggressive patient. With effective use of these techniques, nurses had an increase in confidence in their skills to manage aggressive behavior.

De-escalation training enhanced confidence by increasing the nurses' belief in themselves to be able to respond properly to any given situation with a violent patient (Thackrey, 1987). In various studies, confidence levels improved after WPV prevention training was implemented (Chang et al., 2022; Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Ming et al., 2019). In a study by Lamont and Brunero (2018), educating and training staff on preventative and proactive WPV measures gives them confidence and empowers them to intervene early and effectively manage aggressive patients.

Workplace Violence Deflection Techniques

WPV deflection techniques were used when a patient was kicking, spitting, biting, pulling hair, or engaged in any other physical contact with the intent to cause harm to the staff member. These examples of physical violence required that staff protect themselves to avoid injury. OSHA (2016) supported using deflection techniques when deemed necessary. Deflection training involved using breakaway techniques to respond when a patient physically attacked a healthcare worker (Lamont & Brunero, 2018; Sharifi et al., 2020). Specific deflection techniques included blocking a kick, and releasing an aggressive patient who grabbed the healthcare worker's clothing, hair, or wrist. Such deflection training exercises allowed staff to practice maneuvers to protect themselves when a patient became violent. Staff reported increased confidence after participating in WPV prevention training programs that included deflection techniques to manage violent behaviors (Chang et al., 2022; Lamont & Brunero, 2018).

Risk for Violence Assessment Tools

The assessment of risk for violence helped healthcare workers identify a potentially violent patient. The WHO (2002) recommended that organizations adopt risk assessment tools to assess risk for violence factors that put healthcare workers at risk. There were many risk-for-violence tools used in the psychiatric setting to evaluate patient behavior to determine the likelihood that the patient became violent; however, within the ED setting, risk assessment tools were limited (Cabilan et al., 2022; Partridge & Affleck, 2018). One cross-sectional study evaluated the Broset Violence Checklist (BVC), which consisted of a tool with six items that assessed the presence or absence of three features indicating a patient's risk of violence (confusion, irritability, and boisterousness) and three actions (verbal or physical threats and attacking objects) that represented types of violence (Partridge & Affleck, 2018). The BVC had

been shown to have acceptable utility, the only limitation is that it was used most often in psychiatric settings (Partridge & Affleck, 2018; Almvik & Woods, 1998). Luck et al. (2007) conducted a mixed-methods case study using a different risk assessment tool called the STAMP (Staring, Tone, Anxiety, Mumbling, and Pacing) to assess observable precursors to violent behaviors. The STAMP tool by Luck et al. (2007) focused on the absence or presence of observable behaviors; however, it did not have a scoring system. Although Luck et al. (2007) described the STAMP tool as acceptable for use in the ED setting, the tool had yet to be validated and lacked predictive psychometric properties (Kim et al., 2022).

A mixed methods study by Cabilan et al. (2022) evaluated the Queensland Occupational Violence Patient Risk Assessment Tool (QOVPRAO) that contained three risk domains: 1) historical record of aggression, 2) behaviors of concern, and 3) the patient's clinical presentation. The QOVPRAO by Cabilan et al. (2022) demonstrated acceptable content and predictive validity in the ED setting after being tested through a rigorous process. The tool used a quick and easy approach to assessing the risk of violence and was shown to be suitable and relevant for application in the ED.

Screening tools such as the BVC and STAMP, were reported to work best in determining the risk of violence in patients; however, rigorous testing of these tools was yet to be done. Accordingly, each organization decided which assessment tool they believe will work best for their facility and patient population. In addition, it was important to remember that the risk assessment tool was only one part of a protocol. Yosep et al. (2023) concluded that other protocol components such as violence-preventative interventions, should be implemented in conjunction with the use of any assessment. The adoption of an accurate and reliable risk

assessment instrument that can be administered by nurses should be mandatory to enhance safety in today's healthcare environment (Gosh et al., 2019).

Restrictive Interventions

Considering the importance of ensuring safety for nurses, the literature included restrictive interventions to manage WPV in healthcare settings. Although recommended as a last resort, when de-escalation techniques had failed, restrictive interventions were necessary to ensure staff safety. Restrictive interventions included the restraint, sedation, and seclusion of a patient. Under provision PC.05.03.09, the Joint Commission (2018) suggested that restraint and seclusion be used only when conventional interventions were ineffective and needed to protect the staff from harm. Knott et al. (2020) emphasized that healthcare providers are protected under the Duty of Care (DOC) Act, which refers to the legal and ethical responsibility to provide reasonable emergent care to a person. Under this statute, restrictive interventions are permissible to protect the safety of staff when they feel endangered.

A study by Knott et al. (2020) emphasized using behavioral response teams (BRTs) to intervene when a person poses a threat to self or others. BRTs involved both clinical staff and security personnel responsible for applying restrictive interventions. Restrictive interventions included subduing a patient and applying mechanical restraints before administering sedation. Another study by Roppolo et al. (2020) opposed restraint and seclusion practices due to the associated physical hazards and patient risks. A risk of respiratory compromise and physical injury was associated with using mechanical restraints (Roppolo et al., 2020). In addition, restraints had been reported to be punitive and inhumane (Butterworth et al., 2022). Overall, the subject of restrictive interventions for assaultive patients is limited and remains controversial.

Additional Workplace Violence Prevention Interventions

Additional studies focused on interventions to modify the clinical setting and mitigate threats posed by an unsafe environment. Some studies involved conducting walk-throughs by unit supervisors (Arnetz et al., 2017, Gillepsie et al., 2014). Although study findings did not always specify what changes were made to each unit, some common interventions had been employed (Huddy, 2017). These included weapon screening, bulletproof glass, posting security cameras, and having security officers on site. A study by Shirbache et al. (2023) found it helpful to post signage of a zero-tolerance for violence policy. Security rounding also increased safety in high-risk areas (Arnetz et al., 2017). A patient alert flagging system had been used successfully to notify staff of a patient's previous violent episode (Okundolor et al., 2021; Spelten et al., 2022). Roppolo et al. (2020) stationed specially trained de-escalation and communication officers at all hospital entrances. These additional WPV prevention interventions fostered a safer work environment for healthcare workers.

A dearth of literature was available on interventions based on the level of violence risk, however, strategies to reduce workplace violence had been widely studied and documented. Recsky et al. (2023) reviewed numerous studies that described interventions for mitigating WPV against staff in hospital EDs where a varied range of intervention types were utilized. Education and training were used in most studies, followed by policies and procedural changes, and environmental modifications to reduce the incidence of WPV. Yosep et al. (2023) suggested that effective WPV prevention training programs should focus on environmental modification, employee policies, and education and training.

Healthcare organizations have implemented QI projects to reduce WPV against staff. These QI projects have been shown to use multifaceted approaches. Okundolor et al. (2021) used

violence screening, briefing huddles, and behavioral response drills to reduce the number of physical assaults on staff. Mallet-Smith et al. (2023) screened patients for the risk of violence at Triage and used a flagging system to alert staff on a patient's potential for violence. Winokur et al. (2018) developed a standardized procedure for ED nurses to administer medication early in the intake process. Conversely, Escue et al. (2023) found a behavioral response team useful in helping de-escalate patients before they became violent. These multifaceted QI projects imply that organizations are working towards finding the best approaches to reduce WPV in their healthcare setting.

Workplace violence is a complex issue requiring a multifaceted approach to mitigate it effectively (Chang et al., 2022; Ferri et al., 2020). To address this issue, WPV prevention programs have aimed at using pre-event, during-event, and post-event measures (Raveel & Schoenmakers, 2019). Pre-event measures included using risk assessment tools, worksite risk analysis, hazard prevention, and safety training education. During an event, de-escalation and self-defense techniques were highly recommended components of violence prevention (Raveel & Schoenmakers, 2019; Wirth et al., 2021). Providing support to victims of violence helped reduce the negative impacts associated with the event. Post-event measures such as counseling and relaxation therapy were shown to reduce the impact of stress trauma on victims of WPV (Yosep et al., 2023). In addition, performing root cause analysis and revising policies and procedures were suggested as part of post-incident actions (Raveel & Schoenmakers, 2019).

Summary and Evidence Limitations

Despite strategic efforts to intervene, WPV remained one of the most significant challenges in healthcare. In a review by Wirth et al. (2021) highlighting interventions to reduce WPV in the ED, most studies positively reduced violence using prevention and protection

strategies in the form of education and training. Although different approaches had been used to mitigate WPV in healthcare, it was evident that more work needed to be done. Organizations such as OSHA (2016) created guidelines to include as part of WPV prevention programs; however, there was no standardized evidence-based approach (Gosh et al., 2019). Healthcare organizations must continue to employ practices and revise WPV prevention policies that best fit their organization. Furthermore, offering emotional support to victims of violence helped to reduce the negative consequences and promoted their well-being (Yosep et al., 2023).

In summary, current evidence showed that WPV in the healthcare setting is a worldwide epidemic. Assessing the risk for patient violence using a screening tool was the first step in creating a WPV prevention program tailored to the uniqueness of the ED setting. This was followed by applying a suitable WPV prevention protocol to mitigate episodes of violence. These interventions focused on providing a safe and violence-free healthcare environment. A successful violence prevention program involved awareness and commitment on the part of nurses and the organization. Providing nurses with the tools they need to address violence in the workplace was a priority to protect their well-being and ensure the best possible care for patients. Taking evidence-based preventative measures to reduce WPV can make a significant difference in ensuring the safety of all involved.

Methods

The aim of this QI project was to revise the current workplace violence prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool and evaluate its efficacy in identifying potentially violent patients in the ED of a large metropolitan public teaching hospital in Southern California. Short-term outcome measures included Triage nurse completion rates of the tool and initiation of assault prevention strategies with high-risk for violence patients. The long-term goal was to reduce the number of WPV episodes in the ED after screening with the new assessment tool. Nurses' perceived confidence in dealing with aggressive and assaultive patients was also evaluated.

Design

A pre-and post-design was used for this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) QI project. Observations were made before and after a new risk-for-violence tool was implemented. The Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) model guided this project to evaluate the practice change using the new screening tool.

Setting

The QI project took place in the ED of a 453-bed tertiary care public teaching hospital owned and operated by the County of Los Angeles. This hospital served as a safety net for many residents who were uninsured or underinsured and relied on the County's Department of Health Services for medical care (Los Angeles County Department of Health Services, 2023.). The medical center provided emergency services for acute medical, surgical, and psychiatric needs. The hospital was a designated Level I Trauma Center, ED Approved for Pediatrics (EDAP), and a ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) receiving center. The ED served an average of 90,000 patients annually and included the treatment of pediatric, adult, and adolescent

psychiatric needs. The patient population that visited the ED included homeless persons, individuals with co-morbid medical illnesses, and patients with mental health and substance use disorders. The ED nurses triaged approximately 250 patients a day.

Usual Triage Process

It was important to understand the Triage process where this QI project took place to illustrate the flow of walk-in patients who are seen in the Triage Unit. Patients entering the hospital were initially screened for weapons by security officers and a metal detector. After being cleared of weapons, the patients needing emergency services were directed to a check-in area where a registered nurse asked for basic demographic information and the reason for their visit. This information was entered into the patient's electronic medical record (EMR). Once the patient was checked in, they received an armband and were directed to take a seat in a designated waiting area to be called for triage.

After the patient was called in for triage, he/she was sent to a private room where they were met by a Triage registered nurse (RN) and a provider such as a nurse practitioner or a medical doctor. In the Triage area, the nurse assessed the patient's vital signs, including blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate, pulse oximetry, temperature, and pain. The Triage nurse asked the patient about their medical history, medications, and allergies. The Triage nurse also assessed the patient for fall risk, suicide risk, domestic violence risk, and risk for violence. Once this information was collected and documented, the nurse and provider evaluated the patient's main reason for coming to the ED. After collecting relevant data, the patient was assigned an Emergency Severity Index (ESI) acuity score based on the severity of their medical condition. The ESI acuity system was a five-level ED Triage algorithm that stratified patients into five groups, with one being the most urgent in need of medical attention to five as least critical

(AHRQ, 2020). The acuity score determined how rapidly the patient was moved from the ED Triage Unit to a treatment room.

Participants

Participants included all RNs working in the Triage Unit within the ED. Currently, 117 nurses are trained to work in the Triage Unit. Inclusion criteria included 1) RNs with over one year of experience in the ED and 2) completion of a nursing Triage training course. There were no exclusion criteria.

Ethical Considerations

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained from the facility and California State University Fullerton IRB prior to the initiation of the project. All nurses who were currently working in the Triage Unit were informed of the project and were invited to participate. Nurses were asked to voluntarily complete the pre-survey electronically.

There were minimal to low risks to participants; however, it was noted that the nature of the survey could elicit memories or feelings of past experiences with ED violence which may be distressing. The PL provided resource links to hotlines and the medical center's employee health resource line if needed. All survey data was de-identified. No identifying data was collected, and the data was reported in aggregate form. The data was downloaded and stored in an Excel file on a password-protected computer in the PL's locked office.

Procedure Using PDSA Framework

The PDSA model guided this project. The aim of this QI project was to revise the current workplace violence prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool. The completion rate of the assessment tool that had been most recently used was 63% (as calculated in the year 2021-2022). The goal was to achieve a

completion rate of at least 80% using the new tool. It was assumed that increasing the risk for violence screening would result in an increase in the number of times staff assault prevention interventions (per hospital protocol) were initiated on at-risk patients. The long-term goal was to decrease the number of physical assaults in the ED overall. The project activities involved forming a team, training Triage nurses, implementing an intervention, collecting, and analyzing pre-intervention to post-intervention data, and deciding if the new process should be adopted or revised and re-evaluated in a new PDSA cycle.

Plan

As part of the project planning, a new validated ED risk for violence screening tool with a risk stratification was introduced. The new screening tool replaced the Historical Clinical Risk Management 20, Version 3 (HCR-20-3), which was added to the EMR in 2020 (Douglas et al., 2014). The HCR-20-3 had never been validated in the ED setting and did not include a violence risk scoring system. In addition, assessment completion of the HCR-20-3 was low at 63%. One of the project goals was to improve the completion rates of the new tool.

After obtaining IRB approval, the QI team was established to aid in implementing the new risk-for-violence screening tool. The QI team included four nurses who collect data for the department, and the clinical nurse specialist (CNS) who was the PL. At the first meeting, the PL presented the results of a comprehensive literature search for evidence-based ED violence prevention and available validated screening tools. The overall recommendation was to use the Queensland Occupational Violence Patient Risk Assessment tool (QOVPRAO) (Cabilan et al., 2022). The recommendation for this tool stemmed from the tool's established predictive validity (95% confidence interval [CI] 0.7–0.81, $p < .01$) and inter-rater reliability (0.67 to 0.75; $p < .01$) (Cabilan et al., 2022). In addition, this tool had been tested in the ED, whereas many tools had

not. Permission was obtained from the author to use the QOVPRAO tool before implementation (Appendix C).

A recommendation was made to pilot the tool in the walk-in Triage area. This was because the Triage area was: 1) a high-risk for violence area, 2) a smaller unit comprised of five Triage rooms, and 3) an easier unit to provide ongoing project surveillance. The QI team assisted in the assessment of outcomes for consideration of the formal adoption of the new tool.

Do

The project was announced to all Triage nurses during the daily pre-shift huddles. During this time the nurses were informed of the project and what participation in the project involved. Participation in the project was carried out in two different ways. One method of participating began with a pre-implementation survey, which was accessed through a quick response (QR) code or a survey link before the education began. The second method for joining the project began during the training phase in which the participant had the opportunity to complete the pre-implementation survey using the QR code just before beginning the education. All participants were asked to complete this survey prior to training. Four weeks were allotted for the completion of the pre-implementation survey. During the four weeks, the training schedule was determined.

To obtain more comprehensive information on each element and its implementation, the PL met with Dr. Joyce Cabilan, the author of the QOVPRAO tool. At this meeting, Dr. Cabilan gave background information and described how the tool appears in the EMR. This was also an opportunity to ask questions about the tool before implementation.

Pre-Implementation Survey

A pre-implementation survey (Appendix D) was administered to the participants before staff training. The survey was formatted electronically using the online survey software Qualtrics

XM. The presurvey was comprised of two sections. The first section incorporated demographic questions regarding age, gender, years of experience working in the ED, highest degree or level of school completed, and number of years of experience in nursing. The second section assessed perceived confidence in dealing with aggressive and/or assaultive patients. The questions on confidence were from Thackery's (1987) Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Instrument (CCPAI). The questions on the CCPAI included: 1) How comfortable are you working with an aggressive patient? 2) How good is your present level of training for handling psychological aggression? 3) How able are you to intervene physically with an aggressive patient? 4) How self-assured do you feel in the presence of an aggressive patient? 5) How able are you to intervene psychologically with an aggressive patient? 6) How good is your present level of training for handling physical aggression? 7) How safe do you feel around an aggressive patient? 8) How effective are the techniques that you know for dealing with aggressive patients? 9) How able are you to meet the needs of an aggressive patient? 10) How able are you to protect yourself physically from an aggressive patient?

Thackrey (1987) defined the construct of confidence as having the self-reliant ability, training, and comfort in intervening both psychologically and physically with an aggressive patient. This construct was intended for the purposes of safety and therapeutic intervention (Thackrey, 1987). The instrument consisted of 10 items valued on an 11-point Likert-type scale (from "very uncomfortable," "very poor," "very unable," "very unsafe," and "very ineffective" to "very comfortable," "very good," "very able," "very safe," and "very effective") (Thackrey, 1987, p. 58). The scoring of the CCPAI was a summation of items 1-10. Lower scores represented less confidence, and higher scores represented greater confidence. The score range was from 10-110. The CCPAI demonstrated good reliability (overall Cronbach's α : 0.92) and

was selected because it is commonly used in workplace violence studies (Ming et al., 2019). Permission to use the CCPAI was obtained from the tool's author (Appendix E).

Post-Implementation Survey

At the end of the pilot, a QR code and link to the post-implementation survey were emailed to the Triage nurses who participated in the project. The post-implementation survey asked the same questions as the pre-implementation survey, in addition to questions asking participants about their experience using the QOVPRAO risk for violence tool (Appendix F). The surveys (pre and post) took approximately 5 minutes to complete. A comparison analysis was done to determine if the change in risk for violence screening tool had any impact on the participant's response to the CCPAI.

Education

The pre-implementation education took place in two locations. First, RNs working in Triage were educated through a live, face-to-face, 30-minute PowerPoint presentation conducted by the PL. The training took place in a classroom adjacent to the ED. Nurses unable to attend the presentation were instructed 1:1 by the PL. The training was conducted over a one-month period.

Second, on the week the project began, at the beginning of the shift, a 5-minute live demonstration of the tool occurred daily in the Triage Unit. Paper copies of the tool were made and were to be used on each patient who arrived for triage. The staff had the chance to review the tool and ask any additional questions before their shift in the Triage Unit began.

The education was scheduled after the pre-implementation surveys had been completed by all participants. The training included: 1) elements of the new (QOVPRAO) tool, 2) a review of interventions based on the patient's risk level (according to the hospital protocol), and 3)

methods for activating an alert for at-risk for violence patients in the EMR. The completed forms were collected by members of the QI team daily.

The QOVPRAO Risk Assessment Tool. The participants were asked to complete the QOVPRAO for each patient triaged. Three risk domains were assessed using the QOVPRAO: 1) aggression history, 2) behaviors, and 3) clinical presentation. The tool evaluated risk from low to high risk for violence and scoring ranged from 0-3.

The nurses were instructed to use the EMR to determine if the patient had a history of aggression or if an aggressive behavioral alert had been documented. If the patient had a history of aggression, they received a score of 1. If the patient did not have a history of aggression, their score was 0. The next area of evaluation on the QOVPRAO was the patient's behavior. If the patient was actively exhibiting violent behaviors such as a clenched fist, being verbally demanding, or verbally threatening, they received a score of 1. If the patient did not exhibit these behaviors, they received a score of 0. Third, if the patient had a clinical issue such as alcohol intoxication, drug intoxication, or exhibiting irrational behaviors, a score of 1 was documented. If the nurses did not identify clinical presentations of concern, the score was 0. A summative score of 0 represented a low risk for violence, 1 was a moderate risk for violence, and 2 or 3 indicated that the patient was at high risk for violence (Appendix G).

Interventions Based on Risk Level. Interventions based on the level of risk in patients were included on the paper form of the screening tool. These interventions followed the hospital's care management protocol named Propensity for Violent Behavior (Appendix H). The following section describes interventions that supplemented the QOVPRAO tool.

Low Risk of Violence. If a patient was identified as low risk for violence (score of 0), the Triage nurse should maintain a safe distance of at least one leg length away. In a calm manner,

the nurse provided timely information and addressed patient concerns. Providing the patient with information on all interventions kept them informed of the plan of care. At this level, it was discussed that the nurse should have an exit plan and never allow a patient to block an exit.

Moderate Risk of Violence. If a patient was assessed as a moderate risk (a score of 1), the nurse was to follow all of the low-risk interventions in addition to initiating the hospital's Propensity for Violence Patient Care Protocol. This protocol listed procedures to enact when dealing with a patient scored as a moderate to high risk. In addition, an alert system on the computer was activated to identify patients who are at risk for violence. Five additional safety interventions that nurses were to enact included to 1) use a two-person approach, 2) set behavioral expectations with the patient, 3) assist the patient in using alternative methods of dealing with aggressive feelings, 4) set clear limits and boundaries on acceptable behavior and provide positive feedback whenever the patient showed any progression toward behavioral expectation, and 5) use alternative methods to manage aggressive behavior, such as de-escalation, verbal redirection, and patient education.

High Risk of Violence. If a patient was identified as high risk (score of 2-3), the nurse was to implement the same interventions as moderate risk and alert the hospital's Code Gold team, if necessary. A Code Gold team should be summoned if the patient becomes violent with the intent to hurt staff or others. The Code Gold team is a behavioral emergency response team (BERT) consisting of staff members (registered nurses and nursing attendants) from the behavioral health departments with experience caring for patients with acute psychiatric disorders. Members of this team receive advanced training in managing assaultive behavior and have the competence to manage potentially volatile situations on non-psychiatric units. In

addition, the hospital Sheriff responds to units where the BERT is summoned. At this level, the patient should be moved to a safe area or room, if possible.

GH Visual Alert for Violence Risk. The Golden Hand (GH) designation has been used by partnering Los Angeles County Department of Health Services acute care hospitals. Developed by one of the associate hospitals, the GH symbol serves as an alert when patients are identified as at risk for violence. The GH is an image of a golden-colored open palm within a red, octagonal background (Appendix I). This symbol was designed to increase awareness among team members that the patient had a high risk for violence and that safety precautions be taken when approaching the patient. When providing direct care to these patients, staff were advised to maintain a safe distance and seek assistance from another caregiver. The GH was triggered on the main patient care track page of the EMR when a patient is at risk for violence. The nurses were instructed on the method to activate the GH in the EMR once the patient was identified as a moderate to high risk for violence.

The initial step involved meeting with QI data extractors to explain the workflow. Then paper copies of the QOVPRAO were placed in each Triage room. To make it easily accessible, these copies were placed in a binder where nurses could easily locate and use the tool on each patient that entered the Triage Unit . Hundreds of copies of the QOVPRAO tools were placed in five labeled binders and placed in each Triage room. The PL and QI team collected the completed QOVPRAO tools daily, scanned them into a secure shared file, entered the data into a shared Microsoft Excel worksheet, and checked for completeness.

Data collection took place from December 26, 2023, to February 3, 2024. Data was collected on the number of patients who were scored at low, moderate, and high risk for violence and the number of times assault prevention interventions were initiated. All collected data from

the pre and post-implementation surveys were exported from Qualtrics to a Microsoft Excel worksheet. The Microsoft Excel worksheets were then imported to Intellectus Statistics (2019) for data analysis.

Study

The software program, Intellectus Statistics (2019) was used to analyze the data. Participants' demographic data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Results of the confidence section of the survey were compared from pre- to post-intervention. Percentages of completed risk assessment tools were analyzed. Descriptive statistics, such as means and percentages summarized the data.

The significance level was set at $\alpha=0.05$. The pre and post-survey confidence in coping with patient aggression scores were normally distributed and compared using a paired sample t-test. Logistic regression analysis was done to compare gender and years of experience in nursing to confidence levels in coping with patient aggression. Free-text responses were also reviewed to identify common themes reported by the Triage nurses on the newly implemented risk-for-violence screening tool. Tables, graphs, and charts were used to display the data.

Act

The results were presented and discussed among the QI team. The project was evaluated for its effectiveness. The PL and QI team were satisfied with the changes in the screening tool and a plan for full implementation and adoption of the new violence prevention protocol was made.

Results

Participant Characteristics

A total of 100 nurses participated in the pre-implementation survey and 76 nurses in the post-implementation survey. Seventy-four percent of the nurses were female and 53% held a bachelor's degree in nursing (BSN). The average age was 25 to 34 years. The average years of experience in nursing was two to four years and experience working in the ED was five.

Participant's demographic characteristics are presented in Appendix J.

QOVPRAO Screening

During the period of data collection, 7,774 patients entered the Triage Unit. Of those patients, 3,857 were screened using the QOVPRAO. Overall compliance on completing the tool was 50%. Of the 3,857 QOVPRAO tools used, 97% (n=3759) of patients were scored as low risk, 1% (n=65) were moderate risk, and less than 1% (n=33) were categorized as high risk for violence. The QOVPRAO scores are listed in Appendix K. No assaults or aggressive behaviors were reported during the pilot period of the QI project.

Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Scale

Results of each question on the CCPAI were reported and compared pre- and post-implementation. Scores ranged from 5.8M (2.5 SD) pre-survey to 6.1M (2.8 SD) post-survey for each question. Summary scores for the pre-implementation survey were 5.79M (2.51SD) and 6.06M (2.75SD) for post-implementation. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine differences in pre-aggregate and post-aggregate confidence levels. The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were not significant based on $\alpha=0.05$, $W = 0.98$, $p = .650$. In addition, a two-tailed paired sample t-test between pre- and post-aggregate data showed no significant change in confidence levels from pre- to post-implementation of the project (Appendix L).

The lowest mean score was for the question, “How safe do you feel around an aggressive patient?” (pre=4.76M, 2.54SD, post=5.02M, 2.92SD), and the highest mean score was for the question, “How good is your present level of training for handling psychological aggression?” (pre=6.56M, 2.44SD, post=6.56M, 2.44SD). The results coincided for both pre- and post-implementation. These results suggested that nurses did not feel safe around aggressive patients; however, felt more confident in handling psychological aggression. The results of the CCPAI surveys are illustrated in Appendix M.

A two-tailed independent sample t-test was significant ($\alpha=0.05$, $t(15)=-2.25$, $p=0.040$) for “How good is your present level of training for handling physical aggression?” between female and male categories (M=5.21, SD 3.21; 9.67, SD 2.31). This finding suggested that the males reported more confidence in handling physical aggression than the females. (Appendix N).

A linear regression analysis was conducted to assess whether years of experience in nursing significantly predicted comfort in working with an aggressive patient. The results were not significant, ($p = 0.819$), indicating that there was no correlation between the level of experience in nursing and confidence level when interacting with an aggressive patient.

Fifty-nine percent ($n=37$) of participants reported that the newly implemented QOVPRO tool adequately assessed risk for violence in patients presenting to the ED. Forty-three percent ($n=27$) felt it was quick and easy to complete. Overall, 54% ($n=34$) of nurses selected to have the QOVPRO replace the current risk for violence screening tool.

Discussion

The aim of this QI project was to revise the current workplace violence prevention protocol by implementing a new validated evidence-based risk-for-violence screening tool. The goal was to evaluate its efficacy in identifying potentially violent patients in the ED. From December 26, 2023, to February 3, 2024, 7,775 patients entered the Triage area. Only 50% of patients were screened for violence by Triage nurses using the newly implemented screening tool. Of the 3,857 QOVPRO tools used, 97% (n=3759) of patients were scored as low risk, 1% (n=65) were moderate risk, and less than 1% (n=33) were categorized as high risk for violence. Most of the patients who presented to Triage during the pilot were scored at a low risk for violence. The Triage Unit was selected for this project because a high incidence of violence has been reported occurring in this location (Oztas et al., 2023; Ramacciati et al., 2019). Ferri et al. (2020) postulated that this increase in violence may be due to the location next to the waiting room, where patients with acute medical and/or behavioral health crises first arrive at the ED. Contrary to previous studies, there were no episodes of WPV in Triage during the project timeline. A longer implementation period could have yielded different results.

It was important to note that many research findings indicated that violent incidents can occur in any area of the ED. The implementation of this project could have been extended into other areas of the department. Mallet-Smith et al. (2023) found that assaultive events surrounding the ED occurred when patients were being discharged (33%), receiving treatment (19%), in transition (17%), and/or waiting for care (15%). This highlights the importance of implementing strategies to address and mitigate the risk of violence in all aspects of emergency care, starting with their initial check-in to Triage.

Post-survey analysis revealed that overall confidence scores on the CCPAI scale were low, meaning nurses did not feel confident about handling aggressive patients. Congruent with Wirth et al. (2021), improving training and support for nurses in managing aggressive patients is crucial. An educational behavior management program may be necessary to impact confidence level results. de la Fuente et al. (2019) found a significant improvement in nurse confidence levels after a behavioral management course. This was consistent with Lamont & Brunero (2018) where nurse confidence levels improved after an educational program and training on managing assaultive behavior.

A surprising finding was that years of experience in nursing was not a significant predictor of confidence level. Years of experience often correlate with increased confidence due to accumulated knowledge and skill refinement (Berlanda et al., 2019). The results of this project were inconsistent with Boles et al. (2023), which identified years of experience as a crucial aspect affecting one's confidence level in caring for aggressive patients. The fact that years of experience in nursing was not a significant predictor of confidence level suggests that other factors might play a more crucial role in determining confidence levels among nurses.

Healthcare organizations are responsible for implementing evidence-based measures to ensure staff safety due to the increase in patient-to-staff assaults. The results of this project are consistent with Gosh et al. (2019) showing that integrating reliable violence risk assessment tools into healthcare settings can be the gateway to enhance patient and staff safety. These tools help healthcare professionals identify potential risk factors and behaviors that may lead to patient violence. By assessing the risk of violence, healthcare professionals can implement appropriate interventions or preventive measures to mitigate the chances of violent incidents from occurring. Utilizing such tools promotes a proactive approach to addressing patient violence rather than

reacting to incidents after they happen. Overall, investing in reliable risk assessment tools is a critical step towards creating safer environments for healthcare providers.

Limitations

While the strengths of this DNP project included successfully implementing a new validated risk-for-violence screening tool, there were some limitations. The timing of the tool implementation was problematic in that the Triage Unit had recently been relocated, which caused challenges in the completion of the tool for every patient. Only 50% of patients were screened with the new tool. Another contributing factor was that the tool was only available as a paper and pencil instrument, whereas the previous tool was found in the EMR where nurses could easily access it. Additionally, the project had time limitations in implementation as the data collection period was only six weeks. Additional time could have yielded different results.

Of note was the fact that there were no changes in nurses' confidence levels in handling aggressive patients from pre to post-implementation of the project. However, the PL only reviewed interventions from the current violence prevention protocol. No new interventions to enhance confidence were introduced.

Implications for Practice

One of the findings of this project indicated that violence risk prevention strategies currently in place are not sufficient to ensure nurse confidence in workplace safety. The use of a validated screening tool is only the first step in the establishment of an effective WPV prevention program. This project aligned with the Joint Commission's (2021) new requirement for organizations to have a process to manage safety and security risks. While the implementation of the QOVPRAO screening tool in the ED was successful, continued evidence-based interventions should be implemented to increase RN confidence in dealing with aggressive patients in the ED.

The results of this project suggest that more is needed to promote nurses' safety and increase their confidence in managing violent patients.

The QOVPRAO risk assessment tool was successfully implemented in the ED Triage Unit and has now been formally adopted by the institution. The violence prevention protocol with the new screening tool will be extended to three other DHS hospitals for implementation. For project sustainability, the QOVPRAO tool will be included as part of the new hire onboarding documentation training and future Triage classes.

Conclusion

WPV remains a persistent issue in healthcare that must be addressed. Organizations must prioritize WPV prevention and improve the safety of nurses who are confronted with aggressive patients. Assault prevention demands a comprehensive and multifaceted approach that involves risk for-violence screening, environmental awareness, continuous education of staff on how to manage assaultive behaviors, and other preventive strategies to provide a safe work environment for nurses (Recksy et al., 2023). By implementing such preventive measures and providing support for staff, hospitals can create a safer working environment for ED nurses and improve overall patient care.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: PDSA Cycle

Figure 1.

The PDSA Model for Improvement

Note: From The W. Edwards Deming Institute (2023a). *Deming on management: PDSA cycle*. (<https://deming.org/deming-on-management-pdsa-cycle/>)

Appendix B

Figure 2: Integration of the PDSA Cycle

Figure 2

Integration of the PDSA Cycle

Appendix C

Permission to use the Queensland Occupational Violence Patient Risk Assessment Tool (QOVPROA)

Appendix D

Pre-Implementation Survey

**Quality Improvement Project
Risk for Violence Assessment in the Emergency Department
Pre-Implementation Survey**

Section 1: Demographics	
1. How many years of experience do you have working in this ED?	0-5 yr 6-11 yr 12-17 yr 18-23 yr 24+ yr
2. What is your age?	<25 yrs 25-34 yrs 35-44 yrs 45-54 yrs 55-64 yrs 65+ yrs
3. How would you describe your gender?	Male Female Non-binary/third gender Prefer not to say
4. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?	RN Diploma in Nursing Associate's Degree in Nursing Bachelor's Degree in Nursing Master's Degree in Nursing Doctorate in Nursing Practice Other
5. How many years of experience do you have in Nursing?	Less than 2 years 2-4 years 5-10 years 11-20 years 21-35 years 35+ years

On a scale of 1 to 11, with 1 being the least to 11 being the most confident (circle answer):

Questions	
Section 2: Confidence	
1. How comfortable are you working with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very uncomfortable very comfortable
2. How good is your present level of training for handling psychological aggression?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very poor very good
3. How able are you to intervene physically with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
4. How self-assured do you feel in the presence of an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 not very self-assured very self-assured
5. How able are you to intervene psychologically with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
6. How good is your present level of training for handling physical aggression?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very poor very good
7. How safe do you feel around an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unsafe very safe
8. How effective are the techniques that you know for dealing with aggressive patients?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very ineffective very effective
9. How able are you to meet the needs of an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
10. How able are you to protect yourself physically from an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able

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Appendix E

Permission to use the Clinical Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Instrument (CCPAI)

Retention: LACOUNTY 3 Year Delete (3 years) Expires: Sun 5/17/2026 2:16 PM

Professor Michael 'Misha' Thackrey <misha@mail.fresnostate.edu>
To: Elizabeth Leon

6 attachments (6 MB) Save all to OneDrive - County of Los Angeles Download all

CAUTION: External Email. Proceed Responsibly

Fresno State seal.jpg

Limited Permission to use "Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression" scale

You are hereby granted limited permission to use my "Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression" scale **subject to the following conditions**

This scale is to be used for research purposes only, pending further validation.

This scale must **not be altered**.

The **wording of each item must not be changed**.

The **11-point anchored response scale must not be changed** (e.g., different number of scale points, omission or alteration of anchors).

To ensure fidelity, any non-English language translation must first be translated from English to non-English and then **independently back-translated** from non-English language back to English.

You forward to me a copy of your research results.

By using this instrument you agree to these conditions.

Limited permission to use this scale is automatically withdrawn if you do not meet each of these conditions

note: this instrument is designed to yield a **single overall score** (sum of individual item values) - analysis of individual items alone will truncate reliability.

I do not charge a fee for use of this instrument.

I attach a copy of this instrument for your reference.

Please confirm by return email your acceptance of the conditions above.

Very truly yours

Michael "Misha" Thackrey PhD
Professor of Psychology

Re: Permission to use CCPAI

Professor Michael 'Misha' Thackrey <misha@mail.fresnostate.edu>

Thu 5/18/2023 2:52 PM

To: Elizabeth Leon <elleon@dhs.lacounty.gov>

CAUTION: External Email. Proceed Responsibly

Outstanding!

I wish you every success and I am eager to learn of your findings.

(great study, by the way)

Michael "Misha" Thackrey PhD
Professor of Psychology

Department of Psychology
California State University
2576 E San Ramon Ave M/S ST11
Fresno California 93740-8039

phone 559.278.2691
fax 559.278.7910

Symptoms:

Charter Fellow Association for Psychological Science
Fellow Western Psychological Association
Fellow Society for Personality Assessment
Fellow American Academy of Clinical Psychology
Diplomate American Board of Professional Psychology
California Psychologist License PSY10284
Head Coach USA Taekwondo National Poomsae Team 2006 - 2008

Pronouns:

anybody
someone
whoever

Appendix F

Post-Implementation Survey

**Quality Improvement Project
Risk for Violence Assessment in the Emergency Department
Post-Implementation Survey**

Section 1: Demographics	
1. How many years of experience do you have working in this ED?	0-5 yr 6-11 yr 12-17 yr 18-23 yr 24+ yr
2. What is your age?	<25 yrs 25-34 yrs 35-44 yrs 45-54 yrs 55-64 yrs 65+ yrs
3. How would you describe your gender?	Male Female Non-binary/third gender Prefer not to say
4. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?	RN Diploma in Nursing Associate's Degree in Nursing Bachelor's Degree in Nursing Master's Degree in Nursing Doctorate in Nursing Practice Other
5. How many years of experience do you have in Nursing?	Less than 2 years 2-4 years 5-10 years 11-20 years 21-35 years 35+ years

On a scale of 1 to 11, with 1 being the least to 11 being the most confident (circle answer):

Questions	
Section 2: Confidence	
1. How comfortable are you working with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very uncomfortable very comfortable
2. How good is your present level of training for handling psychological aggression?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very poor very good
3. How able are you to intervene physically with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
4. How self-assured do you feel in the presence of an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 not very self-assured very self-assured
5. How able are you to intervene psychologically with an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
6. How good is your present level of training for handling physical aggression?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very poor very good
7. How safe do you feel around an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unsafe very safe
8. How effective are the techniques that you know for dealing with aggressive patients?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very ineffective very effective
9. How able are you to meet the needs of an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able
10. How able are you to protect yourself physically from an aggressive patient?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 very unable very able

Thackrey, M. (1987). Clinician confidence in coping with patient aggression: Assessment and enhancement. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice, 18*(1), 57-60. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7028.18.1.57>

Additional Questions:	
1. Do you feel the QOVPRAO tool adequately identified patients at risk for violence?	Yes No Not Sure
2. What did you like best about the QOVPRAO?	Easy to complete Quickly assesses risk Other
3. What did you like least about the QOVPRAO?	Time consuming to complete Does not adequately assess risk Difficult to score Other
4. Which risk assessment tool would you prefer to use in the ED	Use the QOVPRAO tool Keep the current violence screening tool (in Cerner) Choose another tool Not sure

Appendix G

QOVPROA Risk Assessment Tool With Safety Interventions

DATE:

MRN:

Los Angeles County Department of Health Services
VIOLENCE PREVENTION SCREENING
 Queensland Occupational Violence Patient Risk Assessment Tool (QOVPROA)

Does the patient have any of the following:

RISK DOMAINS	QUALIFYING CHARACTERISTICS	RESPONSES
Aggression history	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Known history of aggression Alert for aggressive behavior 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No= 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Behavioral concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angry Clenched fist Demanding Resisting care Threatening language Other concerning behaviors 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No= 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Clinical presentation of concern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alcohol intoxication Drug intoxication Erratic or irrational cognition 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No= 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Scoring	Low Moderate High	Yes = 0 <input type="checkbox"/> Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Yes = 2-3 <input type="checkbox"/>

Cobbins, C.J., McRae, J., Learmont, D., Gattuso, K., Galbraith, S., Mason, D., Liley, R., Gattuso, C. & Johnson, A.N.B. (2022). Validity and reliability of the novel three-item occupational violence patient risk assessment tool. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 76(1176-1185). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15105a>

Interventions and Safety Precautions		
Low risk (score = 0) <input type="checkbox"/>	Moderate risk (score = 1) <input type="checkbox"/>	High risk (score = 2-3) <input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain a safe distance of at least one leg length away Communicate in a calm, concise, and clear manner Inform the patient that they are in a safe environment Explain all procedures/interventions to patient/family Provide timely information to address patient concerns Perform periodic rounding per unit protocol Never allow a patient to come between you and the exit 	Follow all low-risk interventions AND: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiate Propensity for Violent Behavior care protocol Activate Golden Hand procedures (per institution) Use a two-person approach Remove any hazardous items/unnecessary medical equipment Set clear limits and boundaries on acceptable behavior and provide positive feedback Use less restrictive interventions such as but not limited to de-escalation and verbal redirection Collaborate with the patient and interdisciplinary team to find appropriate interventions 	Follow all low and moderate-risk interventions AND: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get help to manage patient safely Consider activating Code Gold if the patient is exhibiting violent behavior Consider moving the patient to a safe area/room if possible

Los Angeles County Department of Health Services. Propensity for violent behavior care management care protocol

Appendix H

Propensity for Violent Behavior Care Management Protocol

COUNTY OF LOS ANGELES

HARBOR UCLA MEDICAL CENTER

DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH SERVICES

PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH

PURPOSE: To outline the responsibilities of all staff in the management of the patient identified as potentially violent

WHO MAY PERFORM: All Healthcare Team Members

SUPPORTIVE DATA: Workplace violence is escalating over time. Identification of potential violence helps decrease patient escalation and increase workplace safety. This protocol applies to all patients in Emergency Department and those admitted to the inpatient areas.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Those patients identified having propensity for violence. Example of behaviors indicating propensity: posturing, restless, belligerent, non-compliance

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient who is actively violent or aggressive. The violent patient displays verbal or physical traits and /or physical aggression directed at self, others or against property. Verbal aggression refers to expression of verbal hostility such as statements that seek to inflict psychological harm on another or threats of physical attack. Physical aggression refers to violent action intended to inflict pain, bodily harm, injury or death upon another or self. Aggression against property is the reckless destruction of property.

CONTENT:

INITIAL ASSESSMENT:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assess the following upon admission: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous and present history of violent behavior • Past and present mechanisms for coping with negative emotions • Triggers for violence, if possible • Verbal and non-verbal manifestations of aggressive behavior • Precipitating factors • Need for medication • Need for decreased environmental stimuli 2. Assess for signs of impending violent behavior (posturing, restless, belligerent, non-compliance).
ONGOING ASSESSMENT:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Reassess the following a minimum 4 hours, as per unit reassessment protocol: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal and non-verbal manifestations of aggressive behavior • Precipitating factors • Need for medication • Need for decreased environmental stimuli • Need for toileting, repositioning, or nutrition Assess for signs of impending violent behavior (posturing, restless, belligerent, non-compliance). 4. Identify and report patient with propensity for violence during: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change of shift report, huddles or debriefings

PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH Page 1 of 4

PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH

BEHAVIORAL MANAGEMENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transferring or handing-off care of patient <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Inform patient that he/she is in a safe environment. 6. Communicate with patient in a clear and calm manner. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use non-confrontational verbiage. • Avoid using abbreviations or healthcare terms 7. Address resolution of factor (s) which precipitate violence. 8. Set behavioral expectation with patient: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish clear, simple and enforceable limits • State consequences of behavior • Provide consistent set of expectations and guidance toward self-control 9. Assist patient to use alternative methods of dealing with aggressive feelings/violent urges via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured activities • Quiet time • Time to ventilate feelings 10. Address feelings and/or concerns. 11. Provide positive feedback whenever patient shows any progression toward behavioral expectation(s). 12. Administer medications as ordered to facilitate return to non-violent state. 13. Keep patient updated on plan of care. 14. Provide alternative methods to manage aggressive behavior including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De-escalation • Verbal redirection • Patient education • Family involvement
SAFETY:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Maintain at least one and a half to 3 feet distance from patient at all times. 16. Use a minimum of 2 people when intervening with patient (the "Buddy System"). 17. Remove potentially harmful objects from the patient's room that could be used by the patient to harm self and/or others. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limit presence or sharing of equipment 18. Maintain direct line of sight with patient. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not turn your back to the patient 19. ALWAYS be aware of exit routes when entering a patient t room. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Have an exit plan. 20. Maintain and keep patient in room with low stimulus (e.g., minimizing lighting, minimizing noise and loud conversations) 21. Use non-violent crisis intervention techniques
PATIENT FAMILY TEACHING	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 22. Instruct patient on the alternate methods of dealing with stress, frustration and violent urges prior to loss of control when the patient is calm and ready to learn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal expression of feelings and anxiety • Relaxation techniques (e.g., listening to music preference, watching favorite movies) • Constructive physical activities and coping mechanism

PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH

	23. Instruct family or visitors not to bring materials that patient can use to harm self or others. 24. Educate family or visitors to talk to healthcare staff first before bringing bad news to the patient
REPORTABLE EVENTS:	25. Notify physician immediately when patient: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires restraints/seclusion to control behaviors • Exhibits behavior which may present a risk to self or other 26. Activate Code Gold Team and notify provider and charge nurse if patient requires seclusion or restraints. 27. Implement the Restraints/Seclusion (Harbor UCLA policy 347B) if indicated
DOCUMENTATION:	28. Use screening tools in ORCHID. 29. Document assessment data. 30. Document restraint needs as appropriate.

LEVEL OF EVIDENCE: Level IV(A), VA-B (4)

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Approved by Nancy Blake, PhD., RN, NEA-BC, NHDP-BC, FAAN, and Chief Nursing Officer on March 15, 2021.
Original signature on file.

Protocol and Policy Changes	
Protocol: PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH	Initial Approval Date: 03/15/2021 Revision Dates:
ASSOCIATED STANDARDS (POLICIES, PROTOCOLS, PROCEDURES, etc.)	
<u>Hospital Policy:</u> Policy #347B: Restraints/Seclusion (as appropriate)	
<u>Care Protocols/ Procedures:</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lippincott Procedure: Violent and assaultive patient management (https://procedures.lww.com/lmp/view.do?pld=2525292&hits=management.violence&a=true&ad=false) 	

PROPENSITY FOR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR: CARE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH

Science Levels	Quality Ratings
<p>Level I Experimental study (randomized controlled trial (RCT)) Experimental study method that includes only level I qualitative study Systematic review of RCTs with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>Qualitative Studies A High quality: Consistent, generalizable results; sufficient sample size for the study design; adequate control, definition, conclusions; consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence. B Good quality: Reasonably consistent results; sufficient sample size for the study design; some control, fairly definitive conclusions; reasonably consistent recommendations based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes reference to scientific evidence. C Low quality or major flaws: Little evidence with inconsistent results; insufficient sample size for the study design; conclusions cannot be drawn.</p>
<p>Level II Quasi-experimental study Experimental study method that includes only level II qualitative study Systematic review of a combination of RCTs and quasi-experimental studies, or quasi-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>Qualitative Studies No common agreed-on principles exist for judging the quality of qualitative studies. Like subjective processes based on the identification of study data contribute to synthesis and how much information is contained about the research efforts to meet the appropriate criteria. For meta-synthesis, there is no consensus agreement that quality assessment of individual studies should be made before synthesis across output-quality studies.² A High quality: Used for single studies and meta-synthesis.² The report includes an effort to enhance or evaluate the quality of the data and the overall inquiry in sufficient detail and to describe the specific techniques used to enhance the quality of the inquiry. Evidence of the use of the following is included in the report: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Transparency: Describes how information was documented to justify decisions, how data were reviewed by others, and how themes and categories were formulated. ■ Diligence: Reads and re-reads data to check interpretations, seeks opportunity to find multiple sources to corroborate evidence. ■ Verification: The process of checking, confirming, and ensuring methodologic coherence. ■ Self-reflection and -scrutiny: Being continuously aware of how a researcher's experience, background, or prejudices might shape and bias analysis and interpretations. ■ Participant-driven inquiry: Participants shape the scope and breadth of questions; analysis and interpretation give voice to those who participated. ■ Inightful interpretation: Data and knowledge are linked in meaningful ways to relevant literature. C Low quality: Studies contribute little to the overall view of findings and the value of the literature selected for high quality.</p>
<p>Level III Nonexperimental study Systematic review of a combination of RCTs, quasi-experimental and nonexperimental studies, or nonexperimental studies only, without meta-analysis Exploratory, convergent, or multiphase mixed methods studies Experimental study method that includes only level III qualitative study Qualitative study meta-synthesis</p>	<p>A High quality: Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, or private organization or a government agency; documentation of a systematic literature search strategy; consistent results with sufficient number of well-designed studies; criteria-based evaluation of overall evidence; high-quality, structured evidence; definitive conclusions; national expert-level evidence developed or reviewed within the past 5 years. B Good quality: Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, or private organization or a government agency; reasonably thorough and appropriate systematic literature search strategy; reasonably consistent results; sufficient number of well-designed studies; evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies with fairly definitive conclusions; national expert-level evidence developed or reviewed within the past 5 years. C Low quality or major flaws: Material not sponsored by an official organization or agency; undefined, poorly defined, or limited literature search strategy; no evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies; insufficient evidence with inconsistent results; conclusions cannot be drawn; not reviewed within the past 5 years.</p>
<p>Level IV Based on experiential and nonresearch evidence Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Integrative reviews ■ Literature reviews ■ Quality improvement, program, or financial evaluation ■ Case reports Opinion of nationally recognized expert(s) based on experiential evidence</p>	<p>Organizational Experience (quality improvement, program or financial evaluation) A High quality: Clear aims and objectives; consistent results across multiple settings; formal quality improvement, financial, or program evaluation methods used; definitions and measures consistent; recommendations with thorough reference to scientific evidence. B Good quality: Clear aims and objectives; consistent results in single setting; formal quality improvement, financial, or program evaluation methods used; reasonably consistent recommendations with some reference to scientific evidence. C Low quality or major flaws: Unclear or missing aims and objectives; inconsistent results; poorly defined quality improvement, financial, or program evaluation methods; inconsistent recommendations. Integrative Review, Literature Review, Expert Opinion, Case Report, Community Standard, Clinician Experience, Consumer Preference A High quality: Expert(s) clearly identify the definitive conclusions; provides a critical rationale; thought leader; peer-informed. B Good quality: Expert(s) appears to be credible; draws fairly definitive conclusions; provides logical argument for opinions. C Low quality or major flaws: Expertise is not discernable or is dubious; conclusions cannot be drawn.</p>

²Yang, D. & Dearholt, S. (2017). The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-based Practice Model and guidelines (3rd Ed.). Indianapolis, IN: Sigma Theta Tau.

Appendix I
Symbol of Golden Hand

Appendix J

Participant Demographics

Table 1.

<i>Participant Demographics</i>	n=100	%
Years of experience working in ED		
0-5 years	51	51
24 years and over	5	5
12-17 years	7	7
6-11 years	26	26
18-23 years	7	7
Age		
25-34 years	39	39
35-44 years	34	34
45-54 years	18	18
55-64 years	4	4
Gender		
Female	76	76
Male	19	19
Prefer not to say	1	1
Highest degree		
Bachelor's Degree in Nursing	57	57
Master's Degree in Nursing	8	8
Associate's Degree in Nursing	29	29
RN Diploma in Nursing	1	1
Other	1	1
Years of experience in nursing		
2-4 years	31	31
5-10 years	26	26
Less than 2 years	11	11
11-20 years	21	21
21-35 years	5	5
35+ years	2	2

Appendix K

Results of QOVPRAO Scores

Figure 3.

Results of QOVPRAO scores by week

Appendix L

Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Instrument Survey Results

Table 2.

Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Instrument Survey Responses

	Questions	Pre-Survey		Post-Survey	
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1.	How comfortable are you working with an aggressive patient?	5.62	2.70	6.13	2.89
2.	How good is your present level of training for handling psychological aggression?	6.24	2.28	6.56	2.44
3.	How able are you to intervene physically with an aggressive patient?	5.70	2.83	6.24	3.01
4.	How self-assured do you feel in the presence of an aggressive patient?	5.91	2.51	6.13	2.68
5.	How able are you to intervene psychologically with an aggressive patient?	6.04	2.44	6.45	2.60
6.	How good is your present level of training for handling physical aggression?	5.67	2.40	6.05	2.77
7.	How safe do you feel around an aggressive patient?	4.76	2.54	5.02	2.92
8.	How effective are the techniques that you know for dealing with aggressive patients?	5.60	2.40	5.94	2.62
9.	How able are you to meet the needs of an aggressive patient?	6.03	2.37	5.79	2.62
10.	How able are you to protect yourself physically from an aggressive patient?	6.28	2.64	6.31	2.96

Appendix M

Figure 3. Mean Scores for Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression

Figure 3.

Mean Scores for Clinician Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression

Note: No significant change in confidence levels pre-to-post implementation ($p=0.0476$).

Appendix N

Figure 4. Mean Gender Scores for Handling Physical Aggression**Figure 4.***Mean gender scores of "How good is your present level for handling physical aggression?"*